

Vegetation Analysis And Identification Of Weeds On Rose (*Rosa sp.*) Plantations In The Durian Tarung Area, Padang, West Sumatra.

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This research is a literature study between plant ecology and plant physiology. Vegetation analysis is a method used to determine how large the distribution of various species in an area is. Weeds are plants that grow around cultivated plants whose growth is undesirable and generally detrimental because they can inhibit growth, result in a decrease in the quantity and quality of production and can become a nest of pests and diseases. with the analysis of weed vegetation in the durian taruang area, it is expected to know the factors that affect the inhibition of rose growth due to the allelopathy substances produced by the weed.

Vegetation analysis according to Susanto (2012) is a way of studying the composition or composition of types and forms or structures of vegetation. The unit of vegetation studied in the analysis of vegetation is in the form of a plant community which is a concrete association of all plant species that occupy a habitat. Vegetation analysis is a method used to determine the distribution of various species in an area through direct observation (Rohman and Wayan, 2001). According to Greigh-Smith (1983), vegetation analysis is a way to study the composition and or composition of vegetation in the form (structure) of vegetation from plant communities. Community types occur because of different characteristics in species dominance, species composition, canopy layer structure or also growth form (Irwanto, 2007 on Tanalase, 2010).

Some of the weeds have been recognized as weeds in agricultural and plantation production systems. One of them is *Mikania micrantha* Kunth. from the *Asteraceae* family which is very competitive with plants and causes a decrease in the productivity of some plants (Tjitrosoedirdjo, 2005). This weed can inhibit the growth of other plants and can reduce the production of various plantation commodities and industrial forests such as oil palm, rubber, coconut, citrus, tea, cassava, pineapple, banana, teak, acacia, eucalyptus and albasia (Sankaran, 2008). One mechanism by which weeds influence the growth of other plants is to produce allelopathy in the environment (Orr et al., 2005).

To see the effect of allelochemical compounds, it can be known by testing the growth of a plant, namely roses. *Rosa sp.* are used as indicator plants because they grow very fast. In addition, one of the production roses decreased due to the presence of weeds that can harm farmers (Izah, 2009). Weed control is an effort made to suppress the rate of weed breeding so as not to interfere with cultivated plants. Weeds

in agricultural land do not always have to be controlled from beginning to harvest. Control must be carried out at the right time, so that costs, time, and energy can be more efficient. The right time to control weeds is the time of the critical crop period, which is the period when the plant is very sensitive to environmental factors. This period usually occurs at the age of 1/4 or 1/3 to 1/2 the age of the plant (Zakaria and Burhan 1999). Cultivation of various types of plants, both food crops and plantations, cannot be separated from the presence of weeds. Weeds are plants that grow around cultivated plants whose growth is undesirable and generally detrimental because they can inhibit growth, result in a decrease in the quantity and quality of production and can become a nest of pests and diseases. Weed growth must be addressed immediately so that it does not grow rapidly.

Based on research by Zuhri Syam, Solfiyeni Suwirman, and Zozy Aneloi Noli, according to Weeds, weeds are plants that grow in unwanted places, causing harm to human life. Losses caused include the effect of competition (competition) reducing the availability of plant nutrients that encourage the allelopathy effect. Nasution (1986). Allelopathy is a substance that is toxic to plants. This research was conducted to analyze and identify the weeds in the rose (*Rosa sp.*) plantation, one of which is *Mikania micrantha* Kunth. From the description above, it is hoped that the improvement of weed control in rose plantations will result in superior and dominant results.

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